

STATE-OF-THE-ART IN MECHANICAL TESTING OF COMPOSITES

Yu.M. Tarnopol'skii and T. Kincis
Institute of Polymer Mechanics
Latvian SSR Academy of Sciences
Riga, USSR

ABSTRACT

Attempt has been made to evaluate the state-of-the-art in mechanical testing of fibrous composites and select the most promising test methods for advanced composites in tension, compression, shear and bending on flat and ring specimens taking into account world experience. Attention is focussed on selection of the technique, shape and size of specimens, loading scheme and experimental data processing. Selection of the test methods and their areas of application is substantiated by voluminous factual material.

INTRODUCTION

At the present time the fibrous composites of four generations with a polymeric, graphite, metal and ceramic matrices are in different stages of application, fabrication, development and study. The design methods, deformation and fracture models for structural elements of these materials are based, to a great extent, on the information obtained in mechanical testing of a lamina or a packet as a whole. Therefore increased requirements for accuracy and reliability of this information are put forth. In practice, various shapes, sizes and fabrication technologies of specimens and a multitude of various test methods are being employed. Although definite progress has been made, there are significant differences among various test methods in the degree to which they have been investigated. This fact often leads to incomparable results and controversial judgements about the structural capabilities of composites. A realistic approach to mechanical tests for composites requires that the number of deter-

minable characteristics and methods for strength and stiffness evaluation should be strictly specified. This necessitates a critical analysis of the existing methods, their evaluation and generalization. We are witnessing continuous development of new test methods, as well as evaluation and review of existing methods. The reinforcement schemes for composites become ever more complex; a packet of plies is substituted by a spatial reinforcing framework. Widespread use of wound structures has called forth the advent of numerous test methods for circular specimens; this is the area where the progress has been made of late. This allows one to consider from a united standpoint - as to loading scheme - the test methods for flat and circular specimens [1,5].

STRUCTURAL FEATURES OF COMPOSITES

The main features that should be taken into account in mechanical testing of fibrous composites are the anisotropy and inhomogeneity of the materials; difficulties in generating a uniform state of stress in the reference volume of the specimen; a new understanding of St. Venant's principle; selection of the loading scheme and the apparatus for data processing.

The tests performed on a flat and curved lamina - the basic structural element of fibrous composites - lie in the basis of test methods. Testing of a lamina is necessary not only for engineering specification of the material; the design of complex laminated media and hybrid materials is also based on it.

To evaluate the elastic and strength characteristics of composites the mathematical apparatus of the theory of elasticity for anisotropic media has been employed. To accomplish transition from an actual non-homogeneous composite to quasi-uniform anisotropic medium it is necessary to have a sufficient number of structural elements which is different for various types of reinforcing fibers and loading schemes. It is not often taken into account in selection of the specimen thickness, particularly for materials with complex reinforce-

ment schemes and is the cause of essential errors.

The unidirectional fibrous composites are essentially anisotropic materials with low resistance to interlaminar shear and transverse tension. The anisotropy of elastic properties results in the extension of the zone of end effect in the directions of higher material stiffness which is characterized not only by geometry, but also by anisotropy. The strength anisotropy can lead to premature failure of the specimen in grips. The reliability of results is determined not only by the specimen dimensions but also by the extent of realization of boundary conditions, i.e. conditions of fastening and loading of the specimen. Finally, a premature delamination at the free edges of the specimen due to interlaminar stresses, the magnitude and sign of which depend on lamina layup through the thickness, should be eliminated.

TENSION AND COMPRESSION

Tensile tests for flat and circular specimens and compressive test for flat specimens have been standardized in many countries and are fairly reliable. However, the standards pertain only to orthotropic materials in which the axes of elastic symmetry coincide with the specimen axes. Difficulties arise in the case of loading at an angle to the axes of elastic symmetry of the material, in tension of strips of high-strength unidirectionally reinforced materials. To improve the load transfer the end tabs are used made of the material with the modulus of elasticity being considerably lower, but elongation at failure - higher than those of the composites being tested. In tensile testing of a ring by split discs* the validity of results is greatly determined by proper selection of the relative thickness h/R taking into account the material anisotropy, in particular in estimation of the strength σ_{θ}^u in the reinforcement direction. The loading of rings with internal pressure is preferable for determination of σ_{θ}^u .

* Testing by means of a split disc was developed in 1956 in US Naval Ordnance Laboratory (NOL) as a technologic test.

The main technical problem in compression of flat specimens is the kind of load input and ensuring of the specified mechanism of specimen failure. In compression various mechanisms of failure are possible; it is necessary to eliminate the destruction of end faces, the loss of stability and delamination. This is achieved through combined loading - by normal forces along the end faces and tangential forces - side faces. The compressive testing of rings is more complex than tensile testing, though it is equally well established[1].

The problem of specimen testing at an angle to the reinforcement direction has not yet been solved. Experimentators still lack a theory allowing to take the effects plys' interaction into account and evaluate the edge and end effects.

IN-PLANE SHEAR

The fact that there are many test methods and nearly complete lack of standards is the evidence of the difficulties encountered in the experimental evaluation of shear characteristics. The main difficulty in developing shear test methods is the impossibility of generating the state of pure shear in specimens. Practically there is no shear test for composites; the techniques employed differ among themselves by the way and extent of minimization of "ballast" stresses and deformations. There is in-plane and interlaminar shear. The panel shear in a four-link test rig is the oldest test method. This method is not economical and, regardless of a series of refinements, first of all, the way of specimen fastening and force transfer it does not ensure a uniform state of stress in the specimen. During the last years other methods have undergone intensive study - the rail shear test, several methods of tension of an anisotropic strip, three-point square plate twist.

The rail shear test is simple and economical, but it has certain inherent limitations. Around the free edges of the specimen, the state of stress is not one of pure shear; this is the end effect zone. The fixed edges of the specimen are subjected to squeezing in the grip links. The effect of

end zones and the uniformity of tangential stress distribution across the width of the specimen depend on the length-to-width ratio of the working part of the specimen (l/b) and on the ratio of the elastic constants of the material G_{xy}/E_x .

The tensile test of an anisotropic strip with different fiber layups is apparently simple. However, for determination of the in-plane shear strength the anisotropic strips are not used because all the varieties of this test yield underrated magnitudes.

In determining the shear modulus in the plane of reinforcement layup extensive use is made of a three-point loading scheme for square plate twist. However, the experiments must be performed with great care, since very extreme simplifications have been made in the practical realization of this method. The calculational formula is obtained on the basis of the linear theory and is applicable only with small deflections of plates made of materials which are uniform in thickness and orthotropic in axes of the specimen. The specimen must be strictly flat, since the quantity h^3 appears in the calculational formula. The distance from the support or loading point to the apex of plate angles must not exceed $2h$. This method is inapplicable for determination of the in-plane shear strength.

An experimental evaluation of the five different methods has shown that in determination of the in-plane shear modulus all the methods yield comparable results. Still many difficulties should be overcome in developing reliable and accurate methods for evaluating the shear strength.

INTERLAMINAR SHEAR

The three-point bending of relatively short bars or ring segments is the most widely used method for determination of interlaminar shear strength τ_{xz}^u . A refined solution of the problem of bending a relatively short bar of an anisotropic material shows that the state of stress is substantially different from that assumed in the technical theory of bend-

ing; near the point of concentrated loads application the distribution of tangential stresses over the height of the bar has very definite maximums close to the loaded surface of the bar. For relatively short bars of an anisotropic material there are no sections with a constant ordinate of maximum tangential stresses. Moreover, throughout the entire length of a relatively short bar transverse compressive stresses are active and close to the supports and the point of load application high compressive contact stresses are observed. Because of these deviations the experimentally determined interlaminar shear strength τ_{xz}^u decreases as the relative span is increased. Hence the test results of relatively short bars in three-point bending can serve only for a qualitative comparison of the mechanical properties of different composites.

In the determination of interlaminar shear strength on ring segments, a formula for prismatic bars is used. Here, however, it should be kept in view that in these segments, in contrast to prismatic bars, radial interlaminar stresses σ_r are also acting nearly along their entire length, with the direction of their action depending on the loading scheme.

When the segments are loaded with convexity upwards, the stresses are tensile and when they are loaded with convexity downwards, they are compressive; in the latter case, the stresses σ_r oppose the opening of the delamination crack due to tangential stresses $\tau_{\theta r}$ and thus "increase" the resistance of the material to interlaminar shear.

The limitations in the field of application of three-point bending have led to a search for other methods. Good results, particularly for three-dimensionally reinforced materials, are obtained by torsion tests on specimens with an annular groove. It is important to select correct geometric parameters of the groove, i.e. its relative width l/d and the diameter d . Studies have shown that within the range of l/d 0.2+1.0, the length of the working part of the specimen l does not affect the measured

strength τ_{xz}^u . An increase in the diameter of the working part from 5 to 15 mm likewise has no effect on the measured strength τ_{xz}^u , but if the diameter is increased further ($d > 15$ mm) a sharp decrease in the measured strength τ_{xz}^u is observed.

Recently a series of techniques of biaxial loading have successfully been employed for the experimental determination of shear characteristics, but they are either time-consuming or require much material.

TORSION OF BARS AND TUBES

Torsion test on bars with rectangular cross section allows to evaluate shear moduli in two mutually perpendicular planes of the material. The method is also applicable on circular specimens. There are attempts to overcome the difficulties in experimental data processing by discarding the effect of one of the shear moduli. However, this introduces additional error in the experimental procedure which is already very sensitive to errors in the processing of results. The method is not employed for shear strength determination. In determining the shear moduli from torsion test of circular specimens the loading scheme for the ring split along its axis, for which the effect of bending and transverse shear is negligible, is the best from the viewpoint of uniformity of the state of stress. Technically, the scheme with loading at the site of splitting (Douglas ring) is the simplest as to its realization. However, in this case the effect of bending is negligible at $b/h > 3$.

In determining of in-plane shear strength and modulus the standard method is torsion of thin-walled tubes; the disadvantages of the method are: high material consumption, technological restrictions, necessity to have specially designed equipment. Specific difficulties lie in the correct transfer of the torque.

BENDING

Thanks to the simplicity in realization, the bending

tests of fibrous composites are widespread. In four-point bending, the elastic modulus and strength due to normal stresses are evaluated. The three-point bending allows one to estimate also the interlaminar shear modulus and strength. In this case, as said above, the state of stress in bars of highly anisotropic materials with a small relative span must be taken into account which differs greatly from that described in the technical theory of bending. Errors are also possible when the formulas of the technical bending theory are being extended to tests of ring segments. Standards do not allow for these deviations.

The bending of intact rings loaded with two concentrated forces is also rather widespread. With correct selection of specimen dimensions the method allows to evaluate the elastic and interlaminar shear moduli. The method is inapplicable for strength determination.

The use of in-plane bending of split rings for determination of transverse tension strength σ_r^u with good accuracy is a novelty. In other respects, the bending tests have changed little during the last years.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

The short review allows one to state that during the past decade substantial progress has been made in developing shear test methods and in detailed evaluation of the capabilities of the different methods. This offers the possibility of a better understanding and more precise evaluation of the structural potential of advanced composites. However, as before studies of shear strength still encounter many difficulties. A number of methods, particularly those that have appeared in recent years, will need further changes and refinements as experience is accumulated. It must be emphasized that the material we have set forth merely reflects experience in testing fiber reinforced composites of the first generation, which are based on polymeric matrices. Experience in recent years has shown that a number of the methods that have been developed are useful for fibrous composites of the

next generations as well, those with graphite, ceramic and metal matrices. However, for the experience in testing first-generation composites to be carried over to the new materials additional consideration of the specific properties of the matrix will be necessary in all cases.

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